

Studies in Potential Organo-fluorine Oral Hypoglycemic Agents. Part II. Synthesis of Some 1-Aryl-3-alkyl/aryl Sulphonylureas

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Several 1-arylsulphonylureas and 1-aryl-3-alkyl/aryl sulphonylureas have been synthesised to elucidate the structure-activity relationships in oral hypoglycemic compounds.

In view of the interesting biological properties associated with organo-fluorine compounds, a systematic survey of oral organo-fluorine hypoglycemic agents has been undertaken in these laboratories and the syntheses of fluorinated hydantoin and 2-thiohydantoin have already been reported¹. We now report the synthesis of a number of sulphonylureas and their derivatives, having the general structure $\text{ArSO}_2\text{NHCONHR}$, in which variations have been made in the aryl moiety and in the substituents on the amido group. Several compounds like Tolbutamide (I) and Chlorpropamide (II) have been introduced as active oral hypoglycemic agents and the influence of the nature of Ar and R on the hypoglycemic activity has been studied²⁻⁵.

(I) R = Me, n = 3.

(II) R = Cl, n = 2.

In our investigations, we have chosen a fluorinated phenyl group as Ar in view of the reported increase in activity on introducing fluorine and mainly the propyl⁶, butyl⁶, and benzyl⁷ as R because these show optimum activity (Table II).

The biological activity of these compounds is under investigation and will be communicated in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Arylsulphonylureas were prepared by the action of potassium cyanate on appropriate aryl sulphonamides in ethanolic medium⁸. These were then condensed with the

1. Unpublished.
2. Haack, *Arzneimittel-Forsch.*, 1958, 8, 444.
3. Buschig *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1958, 8, 448.
4. Cassidy *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 23, 923.
5. Marshall and Sigal Jr., *ibid.*, 1958, 23, 926.
6. Hofkelt and Jonsson, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1962, 5, 231.
7. Geigy, *Swiss. P.* 261, 773/1949.
8. Das Gupta, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 417.

hydrochlorides of *n*-propylamine, *n*-butylamine, and benzylamine to provide the desired 1-aryl-3-alkyl/aryl sulphonylureas.

Fluoro-hydrocarbons.—Fluorobenzene, 4-methyl-, 3-methyl-, 2-methyl-, 2-methoxy-, 4-bromo-, 4-chloro-, and 3-chloro-fluorobenzenes were prepared by following the method of Balz and Schiemann⁹.

Arylsulphonyl chlorides were prepared by the method of Huntress and Carten¹⁰ by treating the above mentioned fluoro-hydrocarbons in chloroform with chlorosulphonic acid at 0-5°. In some cases, chlorosulphonation was incomplete in the cold, so refluxing was done for 30 to 90 min. The various aryl sulphonyl chlorides were isolated in the usual way.

Arylsulphonamides were prepared by the method of Huntress and Carten¹⁰ by boiling the arylsulphonyl chlorides for 30-40 min. with strong ammonia and pouring the mixture on cold water. The precipitated sulphonamides were isolated as usual and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

1-Arylsulphonylureas were prepared by following the method of Das Gupta⁸ by refluxing together the arylsulphonamide (1*M*) and potassium cyanate (1*M*) in anhydrous ethanol for 8-10 hr. The mixture was cooled and the solid product filtered, dissolved in water at the room temperature, and again filtered. The filtrate on acidification with HCl deposited a white crystalline solid. 1-Arylsulphonylureas were recrystallised from hot water. The compounds prepared are listed in Table I.

TABLE I
1-Arylsulphonylureas.
Ar-SO₂NHCONH₂.

Ar.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.
4-Fluoro-Ph-	165°	C ₇ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂ FS	14.52	14.67
2-Fluoro-5-chloro-Ph-	158°	C ₇ H ₆ O ₂ N ₂ ClFS	12.96	12.67
2-Fluoro-4-chloro-Ph-	155°	C ₇ H ₆ O ₂ N ₂ ClFS	12.28	12.67
2-Fluoro-5-bromo-Ph-	174°	C ₇ H ₆ O ₂ N ₂ BrFS	10.42	10.77
2-Methyl-3-fluoro-Ph-	165°	C ₈ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ FS	14.11	13.79
2-Methyl-4-fluoro-Ph-	174°	C ₈ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ FS	14.02	13.79
2-Methyl-5-fluoro-Ph-	162°	C ₈ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ FS	13.41	13.79
2-Methoxy-3-fluoro-Ph-	169°	C ₈ H ₉ O ₄ N ₂ FS	13.20	13.90

1-Aryl-3-alkyl/arylsulphonylureas.—1-Arylsulphonylurea (1*M*), alkyl or arylamine hydrochloride (1.2*M*) in anhydrous ethanol was refluxed for 8 hr. on a water bath⁸. About half of the alcohol was distilled and the product was diluted with water when a semisolid mass separated which was filtered, washed with water, and extracted by 10% aqueous NaOH solution. The alkaline solution after treatment with charcoal was filtered and acidified with HCl(dil.) when the solid 1-aryl-3-alkyl/arylsulphonylurea was precipitated. This was recrystallised from aqueous methanol. The compounds are listed in Table II.

9. Adams, "Organic Reactions", Vol. V, p. 193.
10. J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1940, 62, 511.

TABLE II

1-Aryl-3-alkyl(arylsulphonyl)ureas.

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \parallel \\ \text{Ar}-\text{SO}_2-\text{NH} \cdot \text{C} \cdot \text{NHR} \end{array}$$

Ar.	R.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
4-Fluoro-Ph.	Benzyl	180°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ FS	10.79	10.88
2-Fluoro-5-chloro-Ph.	n-Pr	109°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ ClFS	11.00	10.86
2-Fluoro-5-chloro-Ph.	n-Bu	125°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ ClFS	10.68	10.37
2-Fluoro-5-chloro-Ph.	Benzyl	135°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ ClFS	9.75	9.34
2-Fluoro-4-chloro-Ph.	n-Pr	175°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ ClFS	11.12	10.86
2-Fluoro-4-chloro-Ph.	n-Bu	120°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ ClFS	10.51	10.37
2-Fluoro-4-chloro-Ph.	Benzyl	138-39°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ ClFS	9.61	9.24
2-Fluoro-5-bromo-Ph.	n-Pr	135°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ BrFS	9.12	9.43
2-Fluoro-5-bromo-Ph.	n-Bu	89°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ BrFS	9.34	9.06
2-Fluoro-5-bromo-Ph.	Benzyl	97°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ BrFS	8.51	8.26
2-Methyl-3-fluoro-Ph.	n-Pr	81°	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ FS	11.85	11.67
2-Methyl-3-fluoro-Ph.	n-Bu	82°	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ FS	11.45	11.11
2-Methyl-3-fluoro-Ph.	Benzyl	133°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ FS	10.25	9.93
2-Methyl-4-fluoro-Ph.	n-Pr	173°	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ FS	11.85	11.67
2-Methyl-4-fluoro-Ph.	n-Bu	151°	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ FS	11.25	11.11
2-Methyl-4-fluoro-Ph.	Benzyl	139°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ FS	10.12	9.93
2-Methyl-5-fluoro-Ph.	n-Pr	132°	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ FS	11.83	11.67
2-Methyl-5-fluoro-Ph.	n-Bu	107°	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ FS	11.00	11.11
2-Methyl-5-fluoro-Ph.	Benzyl	125-30°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ FS	10.25	9.93
2-Methoxy-3-fluoro-Ph.	n-Pr	138°	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂ FS	11.34	11.03
2-Methoxy-3-fluoro-Ph.	n-Bu	113°	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ FS	10.83	10.52
2-Methoxy-3-fluoro-Ph.	Benzyl	183°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂ FS	9.69	9.47

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